

D. 5.5 – Gendering the Targets of SDG7 for gender-sensitive implementation efforts

WP5 – Development of credible pathways for equitable, just and fair energy transitions

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Gendering the Targets of SDG7 for gender-sensitive implementation efforts

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<i>Abstract</i>	The aim of the gEneSys Deliverable 5.5 is to examine EU policy areas related to the targets and implementation efforts for SDG7 targets. The specific aim is to examine and make recommendations using a new gender analysis methodology developed in the gEneSys project specifically for energy transition, based on the Gendered Innovation model, developed in a collaboration between Stanford University and the European Commission

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1. BACKGROUND	1
2. COMPARING SDG7 TARGETS: THE GLOBAL VS EU PRIORITIES	2
3. KEY GENDER ANALYTICAL APPROACH AND CONCLUSIONS FOR STRENGTHENING RESEARCH AND POLICY FROM GENESYS EVIDENCE	3
4. HOW CAN GENESYS HELP IMPROVE PROGRESS TOWARDS RESEARCH ON FAIR AND JUST ENERGY TRANSITIONS	5
4.1 <i>The use of surveys through the gender lens</i>	6
4.2 <i>Addressing gender gaps in education and training</i>	6
4.3 <i>Applying the Gender Innovations Approach (GIA)</i>	7
4.4 <i>Using empirical illustrations: gender dynamics in solar prosumption</i>	7
5. ADDRESSING GENDER GAPS IN THE GENDER TRANSITION-RELATED EU POLICIES.....	8
5.1 <i>REPowerEU: Energy Security and the Acceleration of the Clean Energy Transition</i>	8
5.1.1 <i>Improving Research for REPowerEU through the Gendered Innovations Approach.....</i>	9
5.1.2 <i>Empirical illustration: addressing gender blindness in REPowerEU</i>	10
5.1.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for REPowerEU</i>	10
5.2 <i>The European Green Deal and the socio-economic dimensions of the energy transition</i>	11
5.2.1 <i>Strengthening Green Deal research through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	12
5.2.2 <i>Empirical Illustration: Addressing Gender Blindness in Green Deal Labour Markets.....</i>	12
5.2.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for the Green Deal</i>	13
5.3 <i>SDG7: Affordable and Clean Energy and the Social Dimensions of Energy Access</i>	14
5.4 <i>SDG7: Affordable and Clean Energy and the Social Dimensions of Energy Access</i>	15
5.4.1 <i>Strengthening SDG7 Research through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	15
5.4.2 <i>Empirical illustration: addressing gender blindness in household energy transitions</i>	16
5.4.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for SDG7.....</i>	17
5.5 <i>ERA and EHEA: integrating gender analysis in energy research and innovation</i>	17
5.5.1 <i>Strengthening ERA and EHEA research through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	18
5.5.2 <i>Empirical illustration: gender dimensions in energy consumption research.....</i>	19
5.5.3 <i>Addressing Gender: policy implications for ERA and EHEA</i>	19
5.6 <i>The European Social Charter and the Social Justice Dimensions of Energy Transitions</i>	20
5.6.1 <i>Strengthening Energy Justice Research through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	21
5.6.2 <i>Empirical Illustration: Gender and Social Equity in Clean Energy Adoption</i>	21
5.6.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for the European Social Charter</i>	22
5.7 <i>The Ljubljana Declaration and Gender Equality in Research and Innovation</i>	23
5.7.1 <i>Strengthening Research and Innovation through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	23
5.7.2 <i>Empirical Illustration: Gender Dynamics in Household Energy Transitions.....</i>	24
5.7.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for Research, Innovation, and Energy Transitions.....</i>	25
5.8 <i>European Parliament Committees (FEMM, LIBE, ITRE): Gender, Rights and Energy Governance</i>	25
5.8.1 <i>Strengthening Parliamentary Governance through the Gendered Innovations Approach</i>	26
5.8.2 <i>Empirical Illustration: Gender Norms and Participation in Energy-Based Livelihoods.....</i>	27
5.8.3 <i>Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for Inclusive Energy Innovation Governance</i>	28
6. GENDER AND ENERGY TRANSITIONS ACROSS EU POLICY ARENAS: EVIDENCE AND POLICY DIRECTIONS	28

7. REFERENCES	30
8. APPENDIX	32

1. BACKGROUND

The aim of the gEneSys Deliverable 5.5 is to examine EU policy areas related to the targets and implementation efforts for SDG7 targets. The specific aim is to examine and make recommendations using a new gender analysis methodology developed in the gEneSys project specifically for energy transition, based on the [Gendered Innovation](#) model, developed in a collaboration between Stanford University and the European Commission (Gendered Innovations, 2026).

The target for the gEneSys research has been the need to interconnect the EU gender equality strategy (EC, 2026a) with the EU ambitions for energy transition, and the EU policy areas related to SDG7 because of the overwhelming disconnect between these three areas at research and policy levels.

The EU has a wide array of policies, strategies and legislations contributing to the achievement of energy transition and SDG7 goals, which are often aligned with the EU climate objectives for 2030 and 2050. However, of specific interest to gEneSys and D5.5 are seven areas:

1. The EU REPower plan, which was adopted to reduce the EU dependence on Russian fossil fuels. The plan included action on saving energy, boosting renewables and diversifying energy supplies.
2. The European Green Capital, which targets concerns with the changes in the labour markets
3. Policy documents specific to SDG7
4. Development of ERA and EHEA to facilitate knowledge and training enabling the energy transition process to take place
5. The European Social Charter of the Council of Europe, which promotes collective advancement of human rights
6. The Ljubljana Declaration, which commits EU Member States to adopting regional strategies on energy efficiency and renewable energy in buildings
7. The political priorities of the European Parliament's FEMM, LIBE, and ITRE Committees as explained and supported in the work of the European Parliamentary Research Services (EPSR)

The EU Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) is the key legislation that sets the overall framework to deliver energy savings across the European Union (EC, 2026b). The directive was established in 2012 and revised in 2018 and more recently in 2023. The 2023 EU energy saving plan introduces the requirement that a share of energy savings is achieved with measures targeting energy poverty, low-income households and vulnerable consumers, so to help them benefit from the transition.

Critically to the aims of gEneSys project, the 2023 version of EED promotes the importance of behavioural changes (such as shifting to public transport and using efficient household appliances), awareness-raising campaigns, insulation of buildings, financial incentives for replacing fossil fuel systems with renewables, and expansion of electric vehicles. These conditions need understanding of the gender aspects of behaviour-change since women and men may differ in their attitudes, autonomy, and agency to understand and perform the required behavioural changes.

However, almost universally, the gender dimension has been missing from the EU energy transition-related policy narratives and implementation goals. The gEneSys project has contributed new understanding on why and how gender analysis can help make energy transition fair and just, and in line with the European Commission's 2020-2025 Gender Equality

Strategy (GES) for 2026-2030 adopted by all Member States on 5 March 2026 (EC, 2026a). The aim for the EU's GES strategy is to put forward concrete actions to embed gender equality into every aspect of life, both online and offline, from education and health to work and leadership.

The aim of D5.5 is to provide a foundation for multi-stakeholder and interdisciplinary examinations of the place of gender inequality in achieving fair and just energy transition and enabling women to have a bigger say as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, influencers, and beneficiaries of the European energy transition policy frameworks and activities at EU-wide, Member State, and institutional levels. The Table in section 2.0 aligns SDG7 targets with the global progress indicators and the indicators for the EU and highlights aspects where the gender dimension is relevant. The items highlighted in yellow indicate the need to apply gender analysis methods to decide if gender inequalities are being solved or magnified, and how to bring more women into the ecosystem of research, innovation, and development for energy transition.

2. COMPARING SDG7 TARGETS: THE GLOBAL VS EU PRIORITIES

<i>SDG 7 Targets</i>	<i>Global SDG7 indicators</i>	<i>EU SDG7 indicators</i>
7.1 By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services	7.1.1 Proportion of population with access to electricity 7.1.2 Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology	Energy consumption: primary and final
7.2 By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix	7.2.1 Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption	
7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency	7.3.1 Energy intensity measured in terms of primary energy and GDP	Final energy consumption in households per capita Energy supply: share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumptions
7.a By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology	7.a.1 International financial flows to developing countries in support of clean energy research and development and renewable energy production, including in hybrid systems	Energy import dependency Access to affordable energy: populations unable to keep home adequately warm
7.b By 2030, expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States and landlocked developing countries, in accordance with their respective programmes of support	7.b.1 Installed renewable energy- generating capacity in developing countries (in watts per capita)	

The gEneSys project and other actors interested in the connections between SDG7 and SDG5 have criticised the lack of mention of gender equality concerns in proposed solutions and omitting recommendations to create the so far missing gender equality indicators.

Figure 1. Connections between energy transition and SDGs (from Energy justice and gender: bridging equity, access, and policy for sustainable development Raman et al., 2025)

3. KEY GENDER ANALYTICAL APPROACH AND CONCLUSIONS FOR STRENGTHENING RESEARCH AND POLICY FROM GENESYS EVIDENCE

The fact that SDG7 targets do not mention gender aspects and there is a total absence of gender indicators for SDG7, promotes gender blind methodologies and analyses, such as surveys, used to identify both the need and the progress in achieving the ambitions of SDG7. A critical example is that surveys of the SDG7 target beneficiaries rely on using “household” as the unit of analysis rather than recognising that gender composition and gender dynamics in a household may determine SDG7 implementations and successes (WHO, 2019).

The gender analysis method tested and advanced in the gEneSys project has been the Gendered Innovations originally developed in collaboration between Stanford University and the European Commission to improve quality of research by tackling sources of gender bias. Gendered Innovations includes a suite of analytical approaches to be applied at each stage of research process to ensure that the potential of gender bias creeping into the results is identified and eliminated.

gEneSys is the first project to use and test Gendered Innovations as the Gendered Innovations Approach (GIA) in the context of energy research. The project tested and enhanced the approach by analysing gEneSys research results from the Systematic Literature Review (Cellini et al., 2025) on the nexus of gender and energy; the outcomes of consultations on energy transition pathways; and as in D5.5 applying it to the EU energy related policy interests.

In the context of energy transition, the GIA may recommend the following targets for analysis:

- *Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes* which means accepting that gender differences are or may be relevant. In the context of energy transition this is particularly important when assembling the evidence base to support analysis of individual subsystems and their interactions with one another.
- *Rethinking Concepts and Theories* which means unpicking definitions (e.g., "energy transition") and clarifying understanding of the wording used when energy transition is debated, e.g., "just transition", "energy poverty" etc. This helps understand the influence of formal and informal social institutions, social norms, and gender stereotypes of human behaviour.
- *Formulating Research Questions* which is about scoping the analytical approach to identify gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems (traditional and emerging). The relevant gender question can be for instance how to ensure societal acceptance of radical innovations and understand impacts of environmental degradation of energy infrastructures on women's livelihoods and health.
- *Analysing Sex* means paying attention to essential, unchangeable biological differences and how they influence response to energy poverty, hunger, disease, or changes in environmental conditions, for instance due to polluting household cooking equipment.
- *Analysing Gender* means understanding socio-cultural norms and stereotypes used in society to label an individual as male or female and recognising how socio-cultural differences and inequalities between women and men are maintained by social institutions.
- *Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact* means combining biological and socio-cultural perspectives on the role and behaviours of women and men. For instance, tracking impact of greenhouse gas emissions may involve understanding the gendered nature of energy consumption as it relates to work, or within the household, and how it relates to health and wellbeing.
- *Intersectional Approaches* means paying attention to other human characteristics such as age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, geography, that play a role in defining vulnerability through lack of access to energy supply.
- *Engineering Innovation Processes* means creating socio-technical systems to ensure that energy transition pathways and low-carbon technologies do not propagate gender inequalities embedded in existing technologies. As an example, solar panels are particularly difficult to dismantle, which makes attempts to recycle the components very difficult, contributing to accumulation of electronic waste, but also restricting opportunities for creating employment for women in electronic waste processing sector.
- *Co-creation and Participatory Research* means involving multiple actors and stakeholders in analysis of problems and generation of proposals for solutions. In the context of energy transitions this may mean including the voices of rural, poor, indigenous, or other marginalized communities.
- *Rethinking Standards and Reference Models* means removing gender bias in energy transition where transparency and traceability in procurement of resources, products, and services is needed, for instance to ensure availability and price of energy.
- *Rethinking Language and Visual Representations* means demonstrating the gendered nature of energy transition in a way that can be easily comprehended by non-gender experts and lay persons. This could be by using images, graphics, stories when communicating rationales for gendered energy transitions etc.

The above consideration have underpinned the gEneSys research with the following key conclusions:

- **Gender remains largely invisible in energy-transition governance.** Across the empirical studies examined in this report, gender dynamics consistently shape energy consumption, technology adoption, and participation in emerging energy systems. Yet these dimensions are rarely addressed explicitly in energy policy frameworks.
- **Energy transitions are shaped by social structures as much as by technology.** Household decision-making, gendered labour divisions, access to financial resources, and socio-cultural norms influence who adopts new energy technologies and who benefits from emerging energy markets.
- **Integrating Gendered Innovation Approach to energy transition plans and activities strengthens the evidence base for energy policy.** Applying Gendered Innovations methodologies in research design improves the capacity of studies to identify gendered patterns of participation, technology use, and energy governance, producing more robust knowledge for policy development.
- **Gender-responsive governance improves the effectiveness of energy transitions.** Policies that recognise gender dynamics can enhance participation in energy transitions, improve the design of innovation programmes, and support more inclusive labour markets in the emerging green economy.
- **gEneSys demonstrate the value of linking research, education, and policy.** By integrating gender analysis into energy research and policy discussions, gEneSys demonstrate how policy and research initiatives can contribute to more inclusive and socially responsive energy transitions across Europe.

4. HOW CAN GENESYS HELP IMPROVE PROGRESS TOWARDS RESEARCH ON FAIR AND JUST ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Energy transition is increasingly recognised as complex socio-technical transformations involving technological innovation, behavioural change, institutional adaptation, and new forms of citizen participation. European policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal and REPowerEU emphasise the need for interdisciplinary approaches capable of integrating the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of energy systems (EC, 2026c; EC, 2026,d).

Despite growing recognition of the social dimensions of energy transitions, gender remains largely invisible in many areas of energy research, education, and policy design. Energy systems are frequently analysed primarily through technological, economic, or engineering perspectives, which can obscure the ways in which social relations shape access to energy technologies, participation in energy governance, and the distribution of energy-related benefits and burdens.

4.1 The use of surveys through the gender lens

Gender gaps and biases are common in using surveys to collect information on household characteristics, attitudes towards renewable energy, and motivations for technology adoption etc. is widespread, they frequently omit to record or analyse the gender of respondents (e.g., is the head of the household male or female). As a result, the potential influence of gendered roles and responsibilities within households remained largely unexplored.

There is also little evidence in gender dimensions in household energy practices. Who makes the decision what appliance to purchase or use (is it the washing machine or a TV). Responsibilities related to energy consumption, such as heating management, appliance use, and everyday domestic practices, may be distributed unevenly among household members. Decisions about investments in renewable technologies may also reflect differences in access to financial resources, technical knowledge, or engagement with energy-related information (Inderberg et al., 2008).

Examined through the lens of GIA, research on prosumption could therefore be strengthened through several analytical strategies. These include collecting gender-disaggregated data on participation in prosumption initiatives, analysing household decision-making processes surrounding investments in renewable technologies, and examining how gender interacts with other social characteristics such as income, education, housing tenure, and access to financing.

Approached from this perspective, integrating GIA into research design would enable a more comprehensive understanding of how social dynamics shape participation in decentralised energy systems. Such insights are particularly relevant for policy frameworks seeking to accelerate citizen engagement with renewable energy technologies.

Despite these commitments, many policy frameworks continue to address energy transitions primarily through technological, economic, and regulatory instruments. In doing so, they may overlook how social relations shape participation in energy systems and influence access to emerging energy technologies. Against this background, applying GIA to policy analysis provides a structured approach for identifying gender blind spots in existing policy frameworks and for strengthening the design of more inclusive transition pathways.

Empirical analyses have shown that such omission persists even in contexts where interdisciplinarity and social engagement are explicitly encouraged (EUA, 2017). One example concerns the integration of gender perspectives into research on energy transitions and societal transformations. An assessment by gEneSys project of the EU Energy-SHIFTS project revealed that many studies addressing social innovation, behavioural change, and energy-transition governance did not systematically incorporate gender analysis into research design or data collection (Diaz-Chavez and Evans, 2024). In many cases, surveys and empirical studies examining citizen engagement with energy transitions did not record the gender of respondents or analyse potential differences in attitudes, experiences, or participation patterns (Diaz-Chavez and Evans, 2024).

4.2 Addressing gender gaps in education and training

A similar pattern emerges in analyses of energy education programmes within European universities. A review by the gEneSys project of Master's programmes in energy-related disciplines found that although many programmes emphasised interdisciplinarity and the integration of social sciences, gender analysis remained largely absent from curricula, research training, and programme learning objectives (Evans and Diaz-Chavez, 2025). Even

programmes designed to address societal aspects of energy transitions rarely incorporated analytical frameworks capable of examining gender dynamics within energy systems.

Examined in this way, the evidence suggests that interdisciplinarity alone does not automatically lead to the integration of gender perspectives. While interdisciplinary research can broaden the analytical scope of energy studies, gender inclusion requires the deliberate use of methodological frameworks designed to identify how gender relations shape technological development, social practices, and institutional arrangements. Against this background, addressing gender blindness in energy transitions requires analytical approaches capable of systematically integrating gender analysis into research, innovation, and policy design.

4.3 Applying the Gender Innovations Approach (GIA)

A growing body of scholarship highlights the need for methodological approaches capable of integrating gender perspectives systematically into research and innovation processes. In this context, Gender Innovations (GI) provides a structured framework for identifying how gender assumptions, social norms, and institutional arrangements influence scientific research, technological development, and policy design (Gendered Innovations, 2026).

Rather than treating gender solely as a demographic variable, the Gender Innovations Approach (GIA) examines how gender relations, social roles, and institutional structures shape the production of knowledge and the design of technologies (Diaz-Chavez and Evans, 2024; Gendered Innovations, 2026). This perspective emphasises that integrating gender analysis into research involves more than including women as research participants or reporting gender-disaggregated statistics. Instead, the approach encourages researchers to examine how research questions, methodological choices, and analytical frameworks may inadvertently reproduce gender bias or overlook important social dynamics (Gendered Innovations, 2026). As seen earlier (Section 3), GIA comprises a suite of analytical strategies that can be integrated into research and innovation processes across multiple fields, including energy.

Complementing this methodological perspective, the SHAPE framework (Foulds and Robison, 2017) situates energy research within the broader social and interdisciplinary dimensions of energy transitions. SHAPE provides a lexicon of concepts widely used in energy social science, including energy governance, energy justice, energy citizenship, energy practices, and socio-technical systems. These concepts highlight how energy transitions are embedded within everyday practices, institutional arrangements, and cultural norms that shape how individuals and communities interact with energy technologies and infrastructures. Appendix A summarises the key concepts within the SHAPE lexicon used to analyse the social dimensions of energy transitions.

Within the gEneSys project, both frameworks were employed in complementary ways. GIA provided the primary methodological toolkit for integrating gender analysis into research design, innovation processes, and policy analysis, whilst SHAPE helped situate energy transitions within broader socio-technical debates and educational contexts.

4.4 Using empirical illustrations: gender dynamics in solar prosumption

Empirical research on energy transitions increasingly highlights the role of citizens and households as active participants in the transformation of energy systems. The emergence of distributed renewable energy technologies, energy communities, and new forms of energy

governance has shifted attention towards the everyday practices and decision-making processes that shape energy consumption and production.

One domain where these dynamics are particularly visible is the growing phenomenon of energy prosumption, in which households simultaneously consume and produce energy, for example through rooftop solar photovoltaic installations. Prosumption challenges traditional centralised models of energy production and introduces new forms of citizen participation in energy systems (Kvaratskhelia and Akagi, 2023).

Research examining prosumption initiatives in the United Kingdom and Norway illustrates how household-level engagement with renewable energy technologies is shaped by social practices and institutional contexts (Standal et al, 2020). Surveys conducted with participants in prosumption initiatives show that motivations for adopting renewable energy technologies include environmental concerns, financial incentives, and interest in technological innovation. However, closer examination of the research design used in many of these studies reveals an important gender limitation (Inderberg et al., 2018).

5. ADDRESSING GENDER GAPS IN THE GENDER TRANSITION-RELATED EU POLICIES

Each policy arena is analysed in turn, through examination of its policy objectives, identifying potential gender blind spots, and demonstrating how empirical research can inform more inclusive policy design through the application of GIA.

5.1 REPowerEU: Energy Security and the Acceleration of the Clean Energy Transition

REPowerEU represents one of the European Union's most significant policy responses to the energy crisis triggered by geopolitical instability and long-standing dependence on imported fossil fuels. Introduced in 2022 (EC, 2022), the strategy seeks to reduce reliance on external energy supplies while accelerating the transition towards a resilient and low-carbon European energy system. In practice, the policy combines measures to expand renewable energy generation, improve energy efficiency, diversify energy supply sources, and strengthen energy infrastructure across Member States (EC, 2026d).

Within this policy landscape, REPowerEU places particular emphasis on the rapid deployment of decentralised renewable energy technologies. Large-scale expansion of solar and wind power, accelerated adoption of heat pumps and electrification technologies, and increased production of biomethane form central pillars of the strategy. At the same time, the policy encourages greater citizen participation in energy systems through the development of energy communities and other decentralised forms of energy production (EC, 2022).

Against this background, the success of REPowerEU increasingly depends on the participation of households, communities, and local actors in the energy transition. Decisions about rooftop solar installations, heating technologies, energy efficiency investments, and participation in energy communities are frequently made at the household or community level. These decisions are shaped not only by technological and financial considerations but also by social structures that influence access to resources, knowledge, and decision-making authority.

However, despite its strong emphasis on citizen participation, REPowerEU pays limited attention to the gendered dimensions of these processes. Questions such as who participates in decentralised energy initiatives, who makes decisions about energy investments within households, and who benefits from emerging energy markets remain largely unexplored.

Recognising these blind spots is important not only for advancing gender equality objectives but also for ensuring that energy transition policies achieve broad societal participation and long-term effectiveness. Within this context, research supporting the implementation of REPowerEU can be strengthened through the systematic application of GIA methodologies.

5.1.1 Improving Research for REPowerEU through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research supporting the implementation of REPowerEU can be significantly strengthened through GIA. This framework enables researchers to identify how social relations, gender norms, and institutional arrangements influence the adoption and governance of emerging energy technologies. Rather than treating gender as an afterthought, GIA integrates gender analysis directly into the research process, helping generate more robust evidence for policymaking.

In the context of REPowerEU, several methodological dimensions are particularly relevant for strengthening research on decentralised energy systems, citizen participation, and technological adoption.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to consider whether gender differences influence participation in renewable energy adoption, household energy decisions, or community energy initiatives. Recognising these dynamics ensures that research captures the full range of social processes shaping the energy transition.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting core policy concepts such as energy security, energy independence, and citizen participation can reveal implicit assumptions about technological engagement and decision-making authority. Examining these concepts through a gender perspective helps clarify how social norms and institutional structures influence participation in energy systems.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine decision-making authority within energy systems allows researchers to identify who controls technological infrastructure, who participates in governance processes, and whose voices are represented in emerging energy initiatives.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure provides insights into how everyday practices, social expectations, and access to knowledge influence engagement with new energy technologies.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with other characteristics such as income, education, housing conditions, or geographic location helps reveal which groups are able to participate in decentralised energy systems and who benefits from emerging energy markets.

Viewed through this lens, GIA broadens the analytical scope of energy research beyond technological performance and market dynamics. By identifying the social structures shaping technological adoption and citizen participation, the approach strengthens the evidence base supporting REPowerEU implementation.

5.1.2 Empirical illustration: addressing gender blindness in REPowerEU

A useful illustration of research relevant to REPowerEU comes from a study examining emerging energy communities in Estonia (Meitern, 2025). The research analyses several citizen-led renewable energy initiatives and investigates the institutional and socio-economic conditions shaping their development. The analysis highlights enabling factors supporting community energy projects, including strong local leadership, supportive municipal actors, effective communication strategies, and viable financial models. At the same time, it identifies structural barriers affecting decentralised energy initiatives, such as regulatory uncertainty, limited access to finance, and institutional legacies linked to historically centralised energy systems.

These findings are particularly relevant in the context of REPowerEU, as it promotes the expansion of decentralised renewable energy systems and citizen participation in energy production. Energy communities are expected to play a key role in accelerating renewable energy deployment while strengthening energy security and local resilience. Understanding the governance structures, financial conditions, and institutional environments that support these initiatives is therefore essential for the successful implementation of the policy framework. Yet, when examined through the lens of GIA methodologies, the case study from Estonia can be strengthened in several important respects.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage examination of whether women and men participate differently in energy community initiatives, including roles in project leadership, governance structures, and community engagement activities.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly address gender dynamics could help reveal who initiates community energy projects, who controls technological infrastructure, and how decision-making authority is distributed among participants.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural dimension would provide insights into how social expectations influence engagement with energy technologies, participation in collective governance, and access to technical knowledge.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** An intersectional perspective could deepen the analysis by examining how gender interacts with income, education, age, or geographic location, factors that often shape the ability of individuals to participate in decentralised energy systems.

Viewed through this perspective, integrating these methodological dimensions would enable the research to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics shaping citizen energy initiatives. Such insights are particularly valuable for REPowerEU, where the success of decentralised renewable energy systems depends on broad societal participation.

5.1.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for REPowerEU

From a policy perspective, integrating gender analysis into research supporting REPowerEU can strengthen both the inclusiveness and effectiveness of the energy transition. As decentralised renewable energy systems expand across Europe, policies increasingly rely on the participation of households, communities, and local actors. Understanding how social structures influence participation therefore becomes essential for achieving the objectives of the policy framework.

- **Evidence generation:** Policymakers should support research programmes that systematically collect gender-disaggregated data on participation in decentralised energy systems, household energy investments, and community energy governance.
- **Inclusive participation:** Policies promoting energy communities should address barriers affecting women's participation in leadership roles, governance structures, and technical decision-making processes.
- **Innovation design:** Research and innovation programmes supporting REPowerEU should ensure that emerging energy technologies and infrastructures do not reproduce existing gender inequalities embedded in technological systems.

Hence, integrating GIA into REPowerEU implementation contributes not only to gender equality objectives but also to more effective energy transition policies. Recognising how social norms, institutional arrangements, and access to resources shape participation in energy systems allows policymakers to design strategies that advance energy security, technological innovation, and social inclusion simultaneously.

5.2 The European Green Deal and the socio-economic dimensions of the energy transition

The European Green Deal constitutes the overarching policy framework guiding the European Union's transition towards climate neutrality. Introduced in 2022, the strategy aims to transform the EU into a resource-efficient, competitive, and climate-neutral economy by 2050 while ensuring that the transition is socially fair and economically inclusive (EC, 2022). The Green Deal seeks to achieve these objectives through a wide range of policy instruments addressing energy systems, industry, transport, agriculture, and finance, while simultaneously promoting innovation and green infrastructure investments.

Central to the strategy is the commitment to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, with intermediate targets including a reduction of at least 55 percent by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. These ambitions have been translated into legislative action through initiatives such as the European Climate Law and the broader Fit for 55 policy package, which collectively aim to align EU energy, industrial, and environmental policies with long-term decarbonisation goals. The Green Deal therefore positions climate neutrality not only as an environmental imperative but also as a new economic growth model for Europe, linking environmental sustainability with industrial competitiveness and social welfare (EC, 2022).

Within this policy landscape, the Green Deal explicitly recognises the social and labour-market implications of the energy transition. Structural economic changes associated with decarbonisation are expected to reshape employment patterns across sectors, occupations, and regions. Although aggregate employment impacts are projected to remain relatively limited, the transition is likely to generate substantial labour-market reallocations between green, white, and brown jobs. Employment in highly polluting sectors may decline or undergo significant restructuring, whereas demand for green technologies and services is expected to increase (Vandeplas et al., 2022).

These structural adjustments highlight the importance of addressing the distributional consequences of the energy transition. Research indicates that although the overall employment effects of environmental policies may be modest, the impacts are unevenly distributed across sectors and regions, potentially affecting specific groups of workers more strongly than others (Alonso-Epelde et al., 2024). Employment in carbon-intensive sectors may contract, while new opportunities emerge in sectors linked to renewable energy, energy efficiency, and green innovation, creating a need for targeted policy interventions that support worker retraining, regional economic diversification, and inclusive labour-market policies (Vandeplas et al., 2022).

Against this background, the Green Deal incorporates mechanisms designed to support a just transition. Instruments such as the Just Transition Fund and the Social Climate Fund aim to mitigate socio-economic disparities by supporting vulnerable regions, workers, and households affected by the transition. These initiatives finance reskilling programmes, promote regional development strategies, and support investments in clean-energy technologies while maintaining social cohesion across the Union.

Despite these commitments, the gendered dimensions of labour-market restructuring and participation in emerging green industries remain largely absent from the policy framework. Questions concerning who benefits from new employment opportunities, who participates in technical energy professions, and how access to training and career pathways is distributed across different social groups receive limited attention. Recognising these blind spots is therefore essential for ensuring that the Green Deal's economic transformation is both socially inclusive and equitable. Against this background, GIA provides a valuable framework for strengthening research supporting the socio-economic objectives of the Green Deal.

5.2.1 Strengthening Green Deal research through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research supporting the socio-economic objectives of the Green Deal can benefit significantly from the integration of GIA methodologies. By examining how gender relations, social norms, and institutional structures shape participation in labour markets and technological innovation, GIA expands the analytical scope of research supporting energy-transition policies. Several methodological dimensions are particularly relevant in the context of Green Deal labour-market transformations.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to examine whether gender differences influence access to training, participation in technical professions, and engagement with emerging green industries.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting concepts such as just transition, green jobs, and labour-market transformation can reveal implicit assumptions about who participates in energy-transition economies and whose work is recognised within new economic sectors.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that address decision-making authority within labour markets helps identify how recruitment practices, professional networks, and career structures influence participation in the green workforce.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure provides insights into how stereotypes regarding technical expertise, leadership roles, and professional identity shape access to employment opportunities in emerging energy sectors.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with other characteristics such as education, social status, or geographic location helps reveal structural barriers affecting participation in the green economy.

Viewed through this lens, GIA enables research to move beyond aggregate employment projections and examine the social structures shaping participation in the green workforce. This broader analytical perspective strengthens the evidence base supporting the Green Deal's socio-economic objectives.

5.2.2 Empirical Illustration: Addressing Gender Blindness in Green Deal Labour Markets

Empirical evidence relevant to the labour-market dimensions of the Green Deal can be found in a qualitative study by Sumarno et al. (2024), which examines women's experiences working

in the energy sector across ASEAN and G7 countries. Based on in-depth interviews with professionals engaged in renewable energy and energy-transition activities, the research explores how institutional environments, workplace cultures, and career structures influence women's participation in the evolving energy workforce.

The analysis highlights several structural barriers affecting women's participation in technical and leadership roles within the energy sector. Interviewees describe persistent gender segregation within engineering and technical professions, limited access to professional networks, and enduring stereotypes regarding women's suitability for technical energy roles. Recruitment practices and career-advancement pathways frequently favour male-dominated professional networks, reinforcing existing gender imbalances across the sector.

These findings are particularly relevant in the context of the Green Deal, which anticipates significant labour-market restructuring as economies transition towards low-carbon technologies and green innovation. While the policy emphasises job creation in renewable energy, energy efficiency, and clean-technology sectors, the evidence suggests that without targeted interventions these opportunities may reproduce existing gender inequalities within STEM professions and energy-sector employment. Nonetheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage closer examination of how gender differences shape participation in green labour markets, including patterns of entry into technical professions and access to training pathways.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly address decision-making authority within organisations could reveal how recruitment practices, professional networks, and workplace hierarchies influence women's career trajectories.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural dimension would provide insights into how stereotypes regarding technical competence and leadership affect participation in emerging green industries.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with other characteristics such as educational background, professional experience, or geographic context could reveal additional barriers affecting participation in the green workforce.

Incorporating these methodological dimensions in combination would enable the research to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics shaping labour-market transformations associated with the Green Deal.

5.2.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for the Green Deal

From a policy perspective, integrating gender analysis into research supporting the Green Deal can significantly strengthen the inclusiveness and effectiveness of labour-market transformation strategies. As Europe expands investment in renewable energy, clean technologies, and green infrastructure, ensuring equitable access to emerging employment opportunities becomes increasingly important.

- **Evidence generation:** Policymakers should support research programmes that systematically collect gender-disaggregated data on employment patterns, training participation, and career progression within green industries.
- **Inclusive labour markets:** Policies supporting the expansion of green jobs should address structural barriers affecting women's entry into technical professions, including access to training, mentorship networks, and professional development opportunities.

- **Innovation ecosystems:** Research and innovation programmes linked to the Green Deal should promote gender diversity within STEM education and energy-sector employment, helping ensure that emerging industries benefit from diverse talent pools.
- **Participatory governance:** Labour-market policies and regional transition strategies should incorporate gender-balanced representation in decision-making processes, ensuring that diverse perspectives are reflected in the design of transition initiatives.

Clearly, integrating GIA into Green Deal implementation can strengthen both the social legitimacy and economic effectiveness of the transition. By recognising how labour-market structures, social norms, and access to resources shape participation in emerging green industries, policymakers can design strategies that advance climate neutrality while supporting inclusive economic transformation.

5.3 SDG7: Affordable and Clean Energy and the Social Dimensions of Energy Access

Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7) seeks to ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all by 2030 (UN, 2026). The goal recognises that access to modern energy services is fundamental to economic development, poverty reduction, and improvements in health, education, and livelihoods across the world. Reliable energy systems underpin critical sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, communication, and industry, making energy access a central component of sustainable development strategies (UN, 2026).

Despite significant global progress in expanding electricity access, major challenges remain in achieving universal energy access. Recent global assessments indicate that approximately 645 million people may still lack access to electricity by 2030, while around 1.8 billion people could continue to rely on polluting fuels and technologies for cooking if current trends persist (UN, 2026). These energy deficits remain particularly concentrated in developing regions, especially in sub-Saharan Africa and parts of South Asia.

Access to modern energy services is closely linked to broader development outcomes. Reliable electricity enables healthcare delivery, supports educational activities, and facilitates economic productivity. At the same time, the global energy system remains a major contributor to climate change, accounting for approximately two thirds of global greenhouse gas emissions (UN, 2026). Achieving SDG7 therefore requires both expanding energy access and accelerating the transition towards sustainable energy systems.

Within this policy landscape, the social dimensions of energy access play a crucial role. In many regions, energy poverty is closely linked to household labour structures and everyday social practices. Responsibilities related to fuel collection, cooking, and household energy management often fall disproportionately on women and girls. Continued reliance on traditional biomass fuels exposes millions of households to indoor air pollution and associated health risks, with significant implications for wellbeing and livelihoods (UN, 2026).

Despite this recognition, gender dynamics are often insufficiently integrated into energy-access policies. Programmes designed to expand access to modern energy technologies frequently focus on infrastructure deployment and technological diffusion while paying less attention to household decision-making structures, gendered labour divisions, and community-level social networks that shape technology adoption. Against this background, applying GIA can significantly strengthen research supporting the social and development objectives of SDG7.

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Despite significant global progress in expanding electricity access, major challenges remain in achieving universal energy access. Recent global assessments indicate that approximately 645 million people may still lack access to electricity by 2030, while around 1.8 billion people could continue to rely on polluting fuels and technologies for cooking if current trends persist (UN, 2026). These energy deficits remain particularly concentrated in developing regions, especially in sub-Saharan Africa and parts of South Asia.

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Despite this recognition, gender dynamics are often insufficiently integrated into energy-access policies. Programmes designed to expand access to modern energy technologies frequently focus on infrastructure deployment and technological diffusion while paying less attention to household decision-making structures, gendered labour divisions, and community-level social networks that shape technology adoption. Against this background, applying GIA can significantly strengthen research supporting the social and development objectives of SDG7.

5.4.1 Strengthening SDG7 Research through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research supporting the implementation of SDG7 can benefit significantly from the integration of GIA methodologies. By examining how gender relations, social norms, and institutional structures shape access to energy services, GIA enables a deeper understanding of the social dynamics influencing energy adoption and energy use. Several analytical dimensions are particularly relevant in the context of energy access and household energy transitions.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to examine whether gender differences influence access to modern energy technologies, household decision-making processes, and participation in energy-access programmes.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting concepts such as energy access, energy poverty, and clean cooking transitions can reveal implicit assumptions about household structures and decision-making authority that may obscure gendered dynamics.

- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine decision-making authority within households allows researchers to identify who controls financial resources, who makes decisions about energy investments, and whose preferences shape technology adoption.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure helps explain how everyday practices, labour divisions, and social expectations influence the adoption and use of energy technologies.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with other characteristics such as income, education, rural location, or access to financial services can reveal structural barriers affecting households' ability to adopt modern energy technologies.

Examined in this way, the research could offer a more nuanced understanding of the social processes shaping household energy transitions. GIA expands the analytical scope of energy-access research beyond technological availability and infrastructure provision. By identifying the social structures shaping energy use and technology adoption, the approach strengthens the evidence base supporting SDG7 implementation.

5.4.2 Empirical illustration: addressing gender blindness in household energy transitions

Empirical evidence illustrating the social dynamics of energy access is provided by a large-scale study by Vicent et al. (2025), which analyses the adoption of clean cooking technologies across 9,388 households in Uganda. The research investigates how women's empowerment, social networks, and household decision-making structures influence the transition from traditional biomass fuels to modern cooking technologies.

The study demonstrates that women's agency within households plays a significant role in shaping energy adoption decisions. Households in which women have greater influence over household decision-making are more likely to adopt improved cooking technologies and move away from traditional biomass fuels. The research also highlights the importance of community-level social networks, showing that women's participation in local organisations and peer networks can facilitate knowledge sharing about clean-energy technologies and encourage behavioural change within communities.

These findings are directly relevant to the implementation of SDG7, which emphasises the expansion of access to clean and modern energy services. Achieving universal access to sustainable energy requires not only technological solutions but also an understanding of the social structures that shape household energy decisions. Nonetheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage closer examination of gender differences in household energy decision-making, including how women's empowerment influences technology adoption across different social contexts.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly address household decision-making authority could reveal how financial control, access to credit, and negotiation processes shape energy investments.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural dimension would provide deeper insight into how traditional roles associated with cooking, fuel collection, and household management influence energy practices.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with income levels, rural location, education, and access to infrastructure could reveal additional barriers affecting the adoption of clean cooking technologies.

Approached from this perspective, the research could generate a richer understanding of the social processes shaping household energy transitions. Integrating these methodological dimensions would enable a more comprehensive analysis of how social relations influence household energy adoption.

5.4.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for SDG7

From a policy perspective, integrating gender analysis into energy-access strategies can significantly improve the effectiveness of programmes aimed at achieving SDG7. Expanding access to modern energy technologies requires not only infrastructure investment but also policies that recognise the social structures shaping energy practices within households and communities.

- **Evidence generation:** Policymakers should support research initiatives that systematically collect gender-disaggregated data on energy access, household energy decision-making, and technology adoption patterns.
- **Inclusive energy access:** Programmes promoting clean cooking technologies and electrification should address structural barriers affecting women's participation, including limited access to financial services, training opportunities, and information about energy technologies.
- **Community engagement:** Strengthening women's participation in community networks and local organisations can enhance knowledge diffusion and support behavioural change related to clean- energy adoption.
- **Empowerment strategies:** Policies that strengthen women's decision-making power within households and communities can significantly accelerate the uptake of modern energy technologies and improve the effectiveness of energy-access programmes.

In policy terms, integrating GIA into SDG7 implementation strengthens both the social inclusiveness and the long-term effectiveness of energy-access policies. Recognising how gender relations shape energy practices allows policymakers to design strategies that simultaneously advance sustainable energy systems, social wellbeing, and inclusive development.

5.5 ERA and EHEA: integrating gender analysis in energy research and innovation

The European Research Area (ERA) represents the European Union's strategic framework for strengthening research and innovation cooperation across Member States and associated countries. The objective of the ERA is to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation, and technology in which researchers, knowledge, and scientific results can circulate freely across national boundaries. By aligning national research policies and promoting collaboration among institutions, the ERA seeks to improve the effectiveness and global competitiveness of the European research system (EC, 2026e).

Within this policy landscape, the renewed ERA framework emphasises the importance of research and innovation for addressing major societal challenges, including climate change, energy transitions, and digital transformation. The policy agenda prioritises investments that support Europe's green and digital transitions, improve access to scientific excellence, and strengthen collaboration among institutions and stakeholders across the European research system (EC, 2026e).

A central pillar of the ERA is the promotion of gender equality within research and innovation systems. Gender equality has been recognised as a strategic priority since the 2012 ERA Communication framework and continues to be reinforced through Horizon Europe and the ERA Policy Agenda (EC, 2026e). These initiatives promote objectives related to gender equality in research careers, gender balance in decision-making, and integration of gender perspectives into research and innovation content (EC, 2026f). The ERA policy framework also supports institutional transformation through initiatives such as the implementation of Gender Equality Plans, monitoring of gender-equality indicators, and the integration of gender perspectives in research design and innovation processes (EC, 2026f).

Alongside these priorities, the ERA increasingly recognises the importance of intersectionality. Diversity in research systems extends beyond gender alone and includes dimensions such as ethnicity, disability, and socio-economic background, all of which can improve the societal relevance and impact of research outcomes (EC, 2026e; EC, 2026f).

Against this background, energy research represents a critical area where the integration of gender perspectives remains uneven. Energy-systems research has historically been dominated by technical and engineering disciplines, often overlooking the social dimensions of energy production, consumption, and governance. Strengthening the integration of gender analysis within energy research therefore represents an important challenge for both the ERA and the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), particularly as universities and research institutions play a central role in shaping future knowledge production for the energy transition. Within this policy context, GIA provides a valuable framework for strengthening research supporting the ERA's objectives.

5.5.1 Strengthening ERA and EHEA research through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research supporting the ERA and EHEA can be significantly strengthened through the integration of GIA methodologies. By examining how gender relations, social norms, and institutional structures influence research design and innovation processes, GIA expands the analytical scope of energy research and contributes to more inclusive knowledge production. A number of methodological dimensions are particularly relevant within research systems addressing energy transitions.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to examine whether gender differences influence energy practices, technological engagement, and responses to energy-transition policies.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting key concepts used in energy research can reveal implicit assumptions about users, households, or communities. Concepts such as energy consumption, energy behaviour, or technological adoption often appear neutral but may conceal gendered dynamics shaping everyday energy practices.
- **Research questions:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine power relations within energy systems allows researchers to identify how knowledge production, technological expertise, and participation in innovation processes are distributed across different social groups.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure helps explain how expectations regarding technological competence, environmental responsibility, or professional roles influence engagement with energy technologies and research activities.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with age, education, income, or cultural norms can reveal structural inequalities affecting participation in research systems and technological innovation.

From this analytical standpoint, integrating GIA into energy research programmes within the ERA and EHEA enables scholars to move beyond purely technical analyses and examine the social dynamics shaping knowledge production and technological innovation.

5.5.2 Empirical illustration: gender dimensions in energy consumption research

Empirical evidence illustrating the importance of gender-sensitive research design can be found in a large-scale survey study conducted by Schubert et al. (2025). The study analyses how gender dimensions influence energy-consumption behaviour using a dataset that captures multiple socio-cultural variables shaping household energy practices.

Rather than treating gender as a simple binary variable, the research examines how gender interacts with socio-cultural factors such as attitudes towards sustainability, environmental values, and everyday consumption practices. The findings demonstrate that energy-consumption behaviour cannot be explained solely through economic variables or technological factors. Social identities and cultural norms play an important role in shaping how individuals engage with energy use and energy-saving behaviours.

The analysis shows that gendered patterns of behaviour influence a range of energy-related practices, including attitudes towards energy conservation, engagement with environmental policies, and willingness to adopt energy-efficient technologies. The research further highlights that gender differences in energy behaviour are frequently mediated by socio-economic characteristics such as education, household structure, and environmental awareness.

From this analytical standpoint, the study demonstrates the value of moving beyond research approaches that treat gender as a simple demographic control variable. By incorporating multiple gender-related indicators and socio-cultural variables, the research provides a more nuanced understanding of how social identities influence energy practices. Nevertheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage closer examination of how gender influences engagement with energy-saving practices and responses to environmental policies.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting the conceptual framing of energy-consumption behaviour could help clarify how gender identities shape everyday interactions with energy technologies and sustainability practices.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure could provide deeper insights into how social expectations influence energy-related decision-making and technological engagement.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with factors such as education, income, or household structure could reveal additional social dynamics shaping energy-consumption behaviour.

Approached from this perspective, integrating these methodological dimensions would allow the research to provide a deeper understanding of how social identities influence energy practices and technological engagement.

5.5.3 Addressing Gender: policy implications for ERA and EHEA

The empirical evidence discussed above highlights the importance of integrating gender analysis into research and innovation systems addressing the energy transition. Within the ERA

and EHEA frameworks, universities, research institutions, and funding agencies play a central role in shaping the direction of future energy research.

- **Research funding:** Funding programmes can encourage the systematic integration of gender analysis within energy research projects. Building on Horizon Europe requirements related to Gender Equality Plans and the integration of gender dimensions in research content can strengthen both methodological quality and societal relevance.
- **Research training:** Universities and higher-education institutions can incorporate gender-sensitive approaches into energy-related curricula and research training programmes, supporting interdisciplinary collaboration between technical energy research and social science perspectives on gender, behaviour, and governance.
- **Monitoring frameworks:** Monitoring and evaluation systems within the ERA can include indicators that track the integration of gender perspectives within research outputs and innovation processes, enabling policymakers to identify progress and remaining gaps.
- **Research capacity:** Strengthening collaboration between the ERA and the EHEA can support the development of a new generation of researchers equipped with interdisciplinary skills for addressing complex sustainability challenges.

In practice, integrating GIA into research governance within the ERA and EHEA can significantly strengthen the inclusiveness and societal relevance of energy research. By recognising how social identities influence technological innovation and energy practices, research and innovation systems can generate knowledge that better supports inclusive and sustainable energy transitions.

5.6 The European Social Charter and the Social Justice Dimensions of Energy Transitions

The European Social Charter constitutes one of the central human-rights instruments of the Council of Europe, establishing a comprehensive framework for the protection of social and economic rights across European states. Adopted initially in 1961 and revised in 1996, the Charter guarantees rights related to employment, social protection, health, housing, education, and protection from poverty and social exclusion, aiming to ensure that individuals can enjoy conditions necessary for dignity, wellbeing, and participation in social and economic life (CE, 2026g).

The Charter is grounded in the principle that social rights are fundamental human rights and must be protected alongside civil and political rights. As emphasised in the Vienna Declaration of 1993, human rights are universal, indivisible, and interdependent. Within this framework, the Charter functions as a complementary instrument focusing on the social and economic dimensions of wellbeing, including labour rights, access to healthcare, housing security, and social protection (CE, 2026g).

Within the European institutional landscape, the Charter operates alongside European Union law and other international legal frameworks. Many of the rights guaranteed under the Charter are reflected in EU legal provisions related to working conditions, social inclusion, social-security coordination, and protection of vulnerable groups, contributing to a broader European system of social-rights protection (CE, 2026g). The Charter also emphasises protection of vulnerable populations and guarantees of social rights without discrimination, including protections for workers, migrants, children, older people, and persons with disabilities.

Against this policy arena, the principles of the Charter have increasing relevance for energy transitions. Access to affordable and reliable energy is closely linked to broader social rights including adequate housing, health protection, and social inclusion. Rising energy costs, unequal access to clean-energy technologies, and disparities in energy infrastructure can

generate new forms of social inequality. Energy access therefore increasingly intersects with social rights protections, requiring policy approaches that recognise energy systems not only as technological infrastructures but also as components of social justice and human wellbeing. Within this policy landscape, applying GIA can strengthen research examining the social justice dimensions of energy transitions.

5.6.1 Strengthening Energy Justice Research through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research addressing the social dimensions of energy transitions can be significantly strengthened through the integration of GIA methodologies. By examining how gender relations, social norms, and institutional structures influence access to energy services, GIA enables researchers to analyse how energy transitions intersect with broader questions of social equity and human rights. The following analytical dimensions are particularly relevant in the context of energy justice.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to examine whether gender differences influence exposure to energy poverty, access to modern energy technologies, and participation in energy-transition initiatives.
- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting concepts such as energy poverty, energy justice, and energy access can reveal implicit assumptions about household structures and decision-making authority that may obscure gendered dimensions of energy vulnerability.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine decision-making authority within households and communities helps identify how financial control, property ownership, and social norms influence energy investments.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure provides insights into how responsibilities for domestic energy use, including cooking, heating, and household energy management, are distributed among household members.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with income, geographic location, migration status, or employment conditions can reveal structural inequalities shaping access to energy services and exposure to energy insecurity.

From this analytical standpoint, integrating GIA into energy justice research allows scholars to move beyond technological assessments of energy systems and examine the social relations shaping access to energy resources and services.

5.6.2 Empirical Illustration: Gender and Social Equity in Clean Energy Adoption

Empirical research provides important insights into the social dynamics shaping energy adoption. A mixed-methods study by Tereka et al. (2025) offers an illustrative example by analysing gendered determinants of clean energy adoption through a combination of household surveys and focus-group discussions.

The study examines how social roles, household labour divisions, and access to resources influence the adoption of modern energy technologies. The findings show that gendered divisions of labour shape energy practices within households. Women are frequently responsible for energy-intensive domestic activities such as cooking and heating, yet they often have limited decision-making authority regarding investments in new energy technologies.

The research also highlights how unequal access to financial resources and information can affect the adoption of clean energy solutions. Women often face greater barriers in accessing

credit, training opportunities, and technical knowledge related to energy technologies. These constraints can limit participation in energy transitions and reduce the effectiveness of energy-access programmes designed to promote modern energy technologies. Viewed through this analytical perspective, the study demonstrates the value of combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. Nonetheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage deeper examination of how gender differences influence exposure to energy poverty and participation in clean energy transitions.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly address household decision-making authority could reveal how financial control, resource allocation, and negotiation processes influence energy investments.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural dimension could provide further insight into how social expectations shape responsibilities for energy-intensive domestic tasks.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with income, migration status, employment conditions, and geographic location could reveal additional social inequalities influencing access to clean-energy technologies.

Approached from this perspective, integrating these methodological dimensions would allow the research to provide a richer understanding of how social inequalities shape energy adoption and participation in energy transitions.

5.6.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for the European Social Charter

The empirical insights discussed above highlight the importance of aligning energy-transition policies with the social-rights principles articulated in the European Social Charter. Ensuring equitable access to energy services is increasingly recognised as an essential component of social inclusion and economic wellbeing.

- **Energy access and social rights:** Energy policies can recognise the relationship between access to affordable energy and fundamental social rights such as housing, health, and social protection. Policies promoting clean-energy technologies should therefore consider the affordability and accessibility of these technologies for vulnerable households.
- **Energy poverty:** Programmes addressing energy poverty can incorporate gender-sensitive analysis in order to identify groups that face disproportionate barriers to accessing modern energy services and to design targeted support mechanisms.
- **Household labour dynamics:** Labour-market and social-policy frameworks linked to energy transitions can recognise the gendered dimensions of unpaid household labour. Policies that reduce time and health burdens associated with traditional energy use can contribute to improved wellbeing and greater gender equality.
- **Inclusive transition policies:** Energy-transition strategies can incorporate gender-responsive approaches that recognise how social inequalities influence access to energy technologies and participation in emerging energy markets.

In policy terms, integrating GIA into research and policy development associated with the European Social Charter can strengthen the alignment between energy-transition strategies and broader social justice objectives. By recognising how gender relations and social

inequalities shape access to energy services, policymakers can design interventions that promote sustainable energy systems while supporting more equitable social outcomes.

5.7 The Ljubljana Declaration and Gender Equality in Research and Innovation

The Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation represents a key policy commitment within the evolving European Research Area aimed at strengthening gender equality across research, innovation, and higher-education systems (EUI, 2021). Endorsed by European ministers responsible for research and innovation, the declaration emphasises that achieving gender equality is a core value of the ERA and a condition for strengthening the quality, inclusiveness, and societal relevance of research and innovation systems.

The declaration highlights the need for structural institutional change within research systems. These commitments include ensuring gender-equal career paths in research, improving gender balance in decision-making positions, and integrating gender analysis into the content of research and innovation activities. Such priorities reflect growing recognition that gender equality contributes not only to fairness within research institutions but also to scientific excellence, technological innovation, and the development of more inclusive knowledge systems.

Despite progress in recent years, the declaration acknowledges that significant gender inequalities persist across research and innovation systems. Structural barriers such as entrenched gender norms, unequal career opportunities, and persistent power hierarchies continue to limit women's participation in research careers and leadership positions. At the same time, the integration of gender analysis into research content remains uneven across scientific disciplines and technological domains.

Against this background, the declaration calls for coordinated policy efforts that strengthen gender mainstreaming within research institutions, funding programmes, and innovation ecosystems. Measures include the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans, improved monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, and enhanced cooperation among research institutions, universities, funding organisations, and policymakers.

Within this policy landscape, the priorities articulated in the declaration are particularly relevant for energy transitions and sustainability research. Addressing complex societal challenges requires research systems capable of integrating diverse perspectives and recognising the social dimensions of technological change. In this context, applying GIA provides an effective framework for strengthening the implementation of these objectives.

5.7.1 Strengthening Research and Innovation through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Research supporting the objectives of the Ljubljana Declaration can be strengthened through the systematic application of GIA methodologies. By integrating gender analysis into research design and innovation processes, GIA enables researchers to identify how social structures, gender relations, and institutional arrangements shape the development and adoption of new technologies. Several methodological dimensions are particularly relevant for research and innovation systems addressing sustainability transitions.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities encourages scholars to examine whether gender differences influence technological adoption, research participation, and engagement with innovation systems.

- **Conceptual frameworks:** Revisiting key concepts within innovation research can reveal implicit assumptions about technological users, research subjects, or beneficiaries of innovation systems, helping to clarify how gendered dynamics shape research agendas.
- **Research questions:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine gender-related power relations allows researchers to identify how participation in research careers, knowledge production, and technological development is structured across different social groups.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure helps explain how expectations related to professional roles, technological expertise, and leadership positions influence participation in research and innovation systems.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with factors such as age, education, socio-economic background, or institutional context can reveal structural inequalities affecting access to research careers and innovation ecosystems.

Against this background, integrating GIA within research design strengthens both the analytical quality and the societal relevance of research addressing sustainability challenges.

5.7.2 Empirical Illustration: Gender Dynamics in Household Energy Transitions

Empirical evidence illustrating the relevance of gender analysis in energy research can be found in a recent econometric study by Sharma et al. (2025). Using national panel data from India, the research examines how households transition from traditional biomass fuels towards cleaner energy sources such as liquefied petroleum gas and other modern cooking technologies.

The analysis identifies several socio-economic factors influencing these transitions, including household income, education levels, and access to infrastructure. At the same time, the findings highlight the central role of everyday household practices in shaping energy transitions. In many households, cooking remains strongly associated with gendered domestic roles, with women primarily responsible for food preparation and management of cooking fuels.

As a result, women are frequently exposed to the health and time burdens associated with traditional biomass use, including indoor air pollution and time-intensive fuel collection. Despite this central role in household energy practices, women often have limited decision-making authority regarding investments in cleaner energy technologies. Financial decisions related to household infrastructure or fuel purchases are frequently controlled by other household members, constraining women's ability to influence energy transitions even when they are the primary users of cooking technologies. Examined in this way, the study provides valuable insights into the social dimensions of household energy transitions. Nonetheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage deeper examination of gender differences in household energy decision-making and the role of women's agency in shaping technology adoption.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly examine household decision-making authority could reveal how control over financial resources and infrastructure investments influences energy transitions.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural structure could provide further insight into how domestic roles and social expectations influence energy practices and technology use.

- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with factors such as rural location, education levels, and income could reveal additional inequalities influencing energy adoption patterns.

From this analytical standpoint, integrating these methodological perspectives would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how gender relations shape household energy transitions and the adoption of cleaner energy technologies.

5.7.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for Research, Innovation, and Energy Transitions

The empirical insights discussed above highlight the importance of integrating gender analysis into research and innovation policies addressing sustainability transitions. The Ljubljana Declaration provides a strong policy foundation for strengthening gender equality within research systems while improving the societal relevance of research outputs.

- **Research funding:** Funding programmes linked to sustainability transitions can encourage integration of gender analysis into research design, supporting interdisciplinary approaches that examine how technological innovations interact with social practices and institutional structures.
- **Research capacity:** Research and innovation policies can support capacity building for gender-responsive research through training programmes, methodological guidance, and institutional incentives that enable researchers to integrate gender analysis into scientific studies.
- **Innovation ecosystems:** Policies supporting innovation systems can address how gender norms influence participation in technology development, entrepreneurship, and knowledge exchange, while promoting gender diversity in STEM education and research careers.
- **Institutional coordination:** Strengthening collaboration between the ERA and the EHEA can further integrate gender-equality objectives across education, research, and innovation systems, supporting institutional change and gender-balanced participation in research careers.

In practice, integrating GIA into research governance strengthens both the inclusiveness and effectiveness of innovation systems addressing sustainability challenges. By recognising how gender relations shape participation in research and technological development, policymakers can support innovation systems that better reflect the diversity of European societies and respond more effectively to complex societal transitions.

5.8 European Parliament Committees (FEMM, LIBE, ITRE): Gender, Rights and Energy Governance

The European Parliament plays a central role in shaping the legislative and oversight processes of the European Union. Within the Parliament, specialised committees examine legislative proposals, scrutinise EU institutions, and contribute to the development of sector-specific policy frameworks. In the context of gender equality and energy-transition governance, three committees are particularly relevant: the Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality (FEMM, 2026), the Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs (LIBE, 2026), and the Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE, 2026). Within this institutional landscape, the responsibilities of these committees intersect in ways that are directly relevant to the governance of energy transitions. The FEMM committee serves as the primary parliamentary

body responsible for promoting and protecting women's rights and gender equality within the European Union. Its work includes monitoring the implementation of gender mainstreaming across EU policies, promoting equal opportunities in employment and social participation, and ensuring that EU legislation addresses discrimination and gender-based inequalities. The committee also evaluates the gender impacts of EU policies and supports the integration of gender-equality considerations across legislative initiatives (FEMM, 2026).

The LIBE committee focuses on the protection of fundamental rights, civil liberties, and non-discrimination within the European Union. Its work encompasses areas such as justice, migration, data protection, and the safeguarding of citizens' rights within the EU legal framework. Through its legislative and oversight functions, LIBE contributes to ensuring that EU policies uphold principles of equality, non-discrimination, and social inclusion. These priorities are particularly relevant when considering how structural inequalities influence access to resources, technological innovation, and participation in socio-economic transitions (LIBE, 2026).

The ITRE committee plays a central role in shaping EU policies related to industry, research, technological innovation, and energy systems. ITRE therefore directly influences legislative frameworks governing the European energy transition, research funding programmes, and innovation strategies. Decisions taken within this committee can shape the direction of energy technologies, research agendas, and industrial development pathways across the European Union (ITRE, 2026).

These committees collectively form an important policy arena in which gender equality, fundamental rights, and technological governance intersect. Their combined responsibilities illustrate how gender perspectives can be integrated into energy and innovation policymaking within the European Parliament. Within this policy landscape, GIA provides a useful framework for strengthening gender-responsive governance across parliamentary processes.

5.8.1 Strengthening Parliamentary Governance through the Gendered Innovations Approach

Applying GIA to the work of European Parliament committees enables a more systematic examination of how gender perspectives can be integrated into legislative and governance processes shaping energy transitions and technological innovation. Several methodological dimensions are particularly relevant within parliamentary governance structures.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities highlights the importance of ensuring that research and innovation policies respond to the needs of diverse social groups. Given ITRE's role in shaping EU research programmes and energy-innovation strategies, integrating gender-sensitive research priorities can influence the direction of technological development in the energy transition.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Intersectional approaches draw attention to how gender interacts with other social characteristics such as income, ethnicity, geographic location, or access to resources. Applying this perspective allows policymakers to better understand how different groups experience energy transitions and technological change.
- **Innovation processes:** Engineering innovation processes encourages policymakers to consider how technological design and innovation pathways may reproduce or challenge existing social inequalities. Parliamentary committees responsible for research and innovation policy therefore play an important role in ensuring that technological development supports broader social inclusion objectives.
- **Institutional collaboration:** Parliamentary governance also benefits from collaboration between committees with complementary mandates. ITRE shapes technological and

research dimensions of energy transitions, FEMM provides expertise on gender equality and gender mainstreaming, and LIBE ensures that EU policies respect fundamental rights and non-discrimination principles.

- **Policy integration:** Coordinating expertise across FEMM, LIBE, and ITRE enables gender perspectives to inform both technological governance and equality oversight within EU legislative processes.

Within this governance framework, integrating GIA methodologies can help strengthen coordination between committees and support more inclusive innovation governance across policy domains.

5.8.2 Empirical Illustration: Gender Norms and Participation in Energy-Based Livelihoods

Empirical evidence illustrating the importance of gender perspectives in energy innovation can be found in research by Murali (2025), which examines the role of solar technologies in micro-enterprises in India. Based on fieldwork investigating energy-based livelihoods, the study explores how social norms influence women's access to energy technologies and their participation in emerging energy economies.

The research demonstrates that decentralised solar technologies can create new economic opportunities for small businesses and local enterprises. However, participation in these emerging sectors remains strongly shaped by gender norms governing labour roles, technological ownership, and financial decision-making. Women frequently participate in labour-intensive aspects of solar-based enterprises while having limited control over technological assets or financial revenues.

The analysis further indicates that male household members often retain decision-making authority over investments in technological infrastructure and business development. These patterns illustrate how technological transitions may interact with existing social structures and potentially reinforce inequalities when gender-sensitive interventions are absent. Examined in this way, the study highlights the importance of recognising the social dynamics shaping participation in emerging energy markets. Nonetheless, a GIA perspective highlights several ways in which the analysis could be strengthened.

- **Research priorities:** Rethinking research priorities would encourage closer examination of gender differences in participation within energy-based enterprises and access to technological resources.
- **Power relations:** Formulating research questions that explicitly address decision-making authority within households and businesses could reveal how control over financial resources influences participation in energy entrepreneurship.
- **Gender norms:** Analysing gender as a socio-cultural dimension could provide deeper insights into how social expectations shape technological engagement and participation in emerging energy economies.
- **Intersectional dynamics:** Examining how gender interacts with factors such as income, education, or geographic location could reveal additional structural barriers affecting participation in decentralised energy markets.

Integrating these methodological dimensions would then enable the research to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how social norms shape participation in energy-based livelihoods.

5.8.3 Addressing Gender: Policy Implications for Inclusive Energy Innovation Governance

The empirical insights discussed above highlight the importance of integrating gender analysis into energy governance and innovation policy. As the European Union continues to promote large-scale investment in energy technologies and research programmes, ensuring that these processes support inclusive participation becomes increasingly important.

- **Policy oversight:** Parliamentary committees responsible for energy, research, and innovation policy can integrate gender analysis into the evaluation of research funding programmes and innovation initiatives, enabling policymakers to identify barriers to technological adoption.
- **Cross-committee coordination:** Strengthening collaboration between committees can enhance the integration of gender perspectives in energy governance. FEMM's expertise on gender equality can complement ITRE's role in shaping innovation policy, while LIBE's focus on fundamental rights reinforces attention to equity and non-discrimination.
- **Inclusive innovation:** Parliamentary governance structures can support the development of innovation policies that recognise how gender norms influence access to technologies, labour participation, and entrepreneurial opportunities.
- **Energy transition governance:** By incorporating gender-responsive approaches into legislative processes, parliamentary committees can contribute to energy-transition strategies that promote environmental sustainability while advancing social inclusion.

In policy terms, embedding GIA-informed approaches within parliamentary governance strengthens the capacity of EU institutions to design innovation strategies that simultaneously support technological development, economic opportunity, and gender equality.

6. GENDER AND ENERGY TRANSITIONS ACROSS EU POLICY ARENAS: EVIDENCE AND POLICY DIRECTIONS

Across the policy arenas examined in this report, the empirical evidence consistently indicates that gender remains an under-examined dimension of energy transitions, despite its recognised importance within European equality frameworks. Studies analysing energy consumption behaviour, clean energy adoption, energy access, and participation in energy-based livelihoods demonstrate that gendered social roles, labour divisions, and unequal access to resources influence how individuals and households engage with emerging energy systems.

- **Energy practices:** Research on energy consumption behaviour shows that gender intersects with socio-cultural factors to shape everyday energy practices and attitudes towards energy use. Patterns of consumption are influenced not only by technological availability or price signals but also by household roles, responsibilities, and social expectations.
- **Household decision-making:** Studies examining transitions to cleaner cooking technologies illustrate how domestic labour divisions and intra-household decision-making structures influence the adoption of modern energy solutions. In many contexts, women bear the primary burden of energy-intensive domestic tasks while having limited authority over investments in household energy technologies.
- **Economic participation:** Evidence from energy entrepreneurship and micro-enterprise contexts further demonstrates that gender norms influence access to energy technologies, participation in emerging energy markets, and control over financial resources associated with energy-based economic activities.

- Examined in this way, the evidence presented across the empirical studies highlights a consistent conclusion: technological innovation alone does not determine the outcomes of energy transitions. Social structures, institutional arrangements, and gendered power relations play a critical role in shaping who participates in emerging energy systems and who ultimately benefits from them.
- These insights carry important implications across the seven European policy arenas examined in this report, particularly for the design of inclusive energy-transition strategies.
- **Evidence generation:** Integrating gender analysis into the design, implementation, and evaluation of energy-transition policies requires stronger empirical foundations. This can be supported through systematic collection of gender-disaggregated data on energy consumption, technology adoption, and participation in energy systems, alongside the development of gender-sensitive indicators within monitoring and evaluation frameworks.
- **Research and innovation governance:** Within the European Research Area, research and innovation programmes can strengthen methodological expectations by supporting interdisciplinary approaches that integrate intersectional gender analysis into technological design, research agendas, and innovation processes.
- **Institutional coordination:** Parliamentary governance structures can also contribute to strengthening gender-responsive energy policy through closer coordination between committees addressing energy, research and innovation, gender equality, and fundamental rights. Such coordination enables gender perspectives to be embedded more consistently within legislative scrutiny and policy oversight.
- **Inclusive participation:** Energy-transition policies themselves can promote broader societal participation by addressing structural barriers that limit access to energy technologies, training opportunities, and financial resources. Targeted interventions supporting women and other under-represented groups within the energy sector can contribute to more inclusive innovation systems and labour markets.

From this analytical standpoint, integrating gender analysis into energy governance strengthens both the effectiveness and the legitimacy of transition policies. Gender perspectives reveal how energy technologies interact with everyday practices, household decision-making structures, and labour dynamics that shape energy demand and technology adoption.

The work presented through the gEneSys project demonstrates the value of combining empirical social-science research with policy analysis to advance gender-sensitive approaches to energy governance. By connecting research, education, and policy development, the project contributes to strengthening the evidence base required for more inclusive energy transitions.

- **Energy governance:** Ensuring that energy policies recognise the diversity of social experiences is essential for achieving transitions that are both effective and equitable.
- **Research design:** Integrating GIA methodologies into energy research strengthens the analytical foundations needed to understand how social dynamics influence technological change.
- **Policy development:** Embedding gender perspectives within energy policy frameworks helps ensure that the benefits of energy transitions are distributed more fairly across societies.

Against this background, engendering energy policy should be understood not only as a matter of social justice but also as a strategic component of effective energy governance. As

Europe and other regions accelerate the transition towards low-carbon energy systems, integrating gender perspectives will remain essential for shaping transitions that are environmentally sustainable, socially inclusive, and widely supported.

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8. APPENDIX

The 20 keywords within the SHAPE Energy Lexicon encapsulate core SSH themes critical to understanding and addressing energy transitions. These include concepts such as energy behaviour, energy citizen(ship), energy culture(s), energy governance, energy justice, energy policy, and energy transition, as well as more technical-social hybrid terms such as smart and sociotechnical. Each keyword is unpacked through multiple disciplinary lenses to reflect the variety of interpretations and emphases, from the micro-level actions of individuals and communities to the macro-level structures of institutions and governance. For example, energy justice addresses fairness in energy access and impacts, while energy citizenship highlights the active role of people in shaping energy futures beyond mere consumption. The lexicon underscores that words in energy discourse do not merely describe phenomena but shape research priorities, policy design, and public engagement. The origins, definitions, understandings and discussion of the keywords in the SHAPE lexicon are provided in Foulds & Robison (2017)

Table 2 SHAPE lexicon keywords

1. Energy behaviour	11. Energy poverty
2. Energy citizen (ship)	12. Energy practice(s)
3. Energy consumer	13. Energy security
4. Energy culture(s)	14. Energy social science
5. Energy efficiency	15. Energy storage
6. Energy future(s)	16. Energy transition
7. Energy governance	17. Energy engagement
8. Energy justice	18. Low-carbon energy
9. Energy models	19. Smart
10. Energy policy	20. Socio-technical

Source: Foulds & Robison (2017)

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